

THE ROLE OF IDEOLOGY IN THE RISE OF NATIONAL SPIRITUALITY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7517312>

***Abstract.** The importance of the role of national ideology in the development of new Uzbekistan is highlighted in this thesis.*

***Keywords:** nationality, spirituality, idea, ideology, human interest.*

In our country, which seeks to build a democratic state governed by the rule of law and civil society, the national ideology unites all segments of the population and calls for action in the common interest and a common goal. In such an ideology, universal principles are strengthened.

Therefore, the ideology of the society must be the ideological basis of this society, to represent the common man and his interests, to ensure the peaceful life of our people.

National ideology is the embrace of our identity, our sense of sacred traditions, the noble aspirations of our people, the lofty goals and objectives of our society today, the diversity of ideas, contradictions and ideas that exist in our society today, the aspirations and hopes of any category and group. Regardless of their beliefs and worldviews, there must be an ideology that unites them all around a single flag, protects the inviolability of our people and state, and calls our people to the greatest goals. At the same time, our national ideology must be completely free from any nationalism and similar elements, disregard for other peoples and nations, discriminatory attitudes and views, and be the basis and guide for neighbouring states and peoples, the world community in general and the international arena. .

Through the national ideology, the nation unites, sets great goals and is able to achieve them. The unity of the nation and the people is the key to any development.

The inculcation of the national ideology in the minds of military servicemen is directly related to the in-depth study of its goals and objectives.

Every ideology has certain goals. These goals determine the ways, means, and means of achieving the result.

The main goals of ideology are to convince people of a certain idea, to organize around that idea, to mobilize them to implement the idea, to motivate people spiritually, to educate ideologically, to form ideological immunity, to have a program of action.

Ideology, as a system of ideas, aims to propagate any idea, to convince people that the idea is correct, vital, and progressive.

In order to convince the general public that any idea is progressive and humane, it is necessary, firstly, that the idea be close and directly relevant to the life of the people, and secondly, to determine the most convenient means and methods of conveying it to the people.

National ideology is a common program of action of all social strata and groups in society, a means of encouraging them to be active. Article 12 of the Constitution of the Republic

of Uzbekistan states: “Social life in the Republic of Uzbekistan develops on the basis of diversity of political institutions, ideologies and opinions. No ideology can be established as a state ideology. ” This rule means that the program ideas of any of the parties, movements and socio-political groups operating in Uzbekistan can not be a single state ideology. With the inculcation of national ideology in the minds of people, they form a sense of responsibility for the fate of the Motherland, a single homeland. Because if personal ideas and interests are the factor that enhances the activity of the individual, the national ideology reflects the vital interests and aspirations of an entire nation. The national idea and ideology should be based on the ancient traditions, customs, language, religion, psyche, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, national and universal values, the principles of democracy, instill in us a sense of confidence, compassion, patience, justice and enlightenment. Thus, if an idea is a glorious idea that mobilizes, then ideology is a system of ideas that unites, organizes, motivates, and governs such glorious ideas as a whole.

The formation of the national idea and ideology - eliminates the dependence on thought, the slavery of thought, leads to the education of a free-thinking person. As a result, every citizen fully enjoys his rights, fulfills his duties and responsibilities consciously. It is a correct understanding of the tasks before society, knowledge of the laws of use of social experiences, a sense of responsibility to the Motherland, the nation. By understanding ourselves, man remembers the past, compares it with the present, draws conclusions, and on this basis looks to the future.

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